

Perceived Stimulus of Human Resource Development (Hrd) Practices On Climate of Public Universities in Province Of Balochistan, Pakistan

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Abstract

Present study was carried out in Balochistan province, Pakistan so as to determine the respondent's perception based on five-point Likert scale about human resource development practices on climate of public universities: namely BUET, SBK, BUTEMS and UOB Quetta. Two hundred (200) respondents, (50) respondents from each public university were selected by using simple random sampling technique. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 used for the data analyses. Results reveals that significant discrepancy was observed 4 out of 7 categories about HRD climate within public universities, Further, significant alterations were detected five out of seven categories about capacity building programs. Statistical significant variances were also set up 4 out of 7 about constraints statements. Based on achieved outcome following recommendation was put forward. HRD dimension regards as the colossal reassurance tools for enlargement professional capacity, indispensable, part and parcel towards development hierarchy, in this regard HRD practices should be implemented at grass root level so that achieved the desirable output and better conceptual productivity for future development for the employees within work environment
Key words: human resource development, public universities, Quetta Balochistan, Pakistan.

Introduction

In the medieval era, the public universities were devoted to the spirit of knowledge, currently; they need to cover not only knowledge dissemination, but also enquired the entrepreneurial and innovative events (FINHEEC, n. d.). Higher institutions or public universities of learning take on diverse human resource development practices so as to increase the employee learning domain such as knowledge, skills, and attributions as well as stimulate them to work harder in the direction of realizing the set goals (Dessler, 2008). Public universities expand the worth of present workers through the delivering the wide-ranging capacity building programs or trainings and development events. Substantial indication advocates that investments in working out yield create favorable logistic results (Knoke, 1994). Performance management as a process explicitly recognizes that in today's globally competitive industrial environment, every employee's efforts must focus on helping the company to achieve its strategic goals. The term Human Resource Development (HRD) was first create by Leonard Nadler who distinct it as a sequence of prearranged actions which are directed contained by a quantified time spell and planned to yield attitudinal variation. Human resource development climate delivers the window of opportunities for an individual worker performance with the aim of increase the present and upcoming work performance, whereas concurrently preminent using the social capital so as to develop the competence of the institute *per se*.

Human Resource and training are critical events that agencies must deliver emphasis to improve the skill and capability in their staff. Although the terms schooling and improvement are connected, they address barely one-of-a-kind needs. Training specializes in learning the vital abilities and obtaining the expertise required to perform a job. Development makes a specialty of the coaching needed for future jobs. Idyllically, well-implemented and well-developed human resources development systems are essential to the institutes tactical strategy besides advantage mutually the employee and the institutes. Intrinsically, human resource development is a latent instrument for individual, group as well as institution change and revolution. Moral human resource development climate would empower to enhance the staff to their efficiency for better institutional performance. Comprehensive evaluation of literature exposes that maximum of empirical studies were completed about the human resource development (HRD) climate in many government systems either organizational level or public universities level. In this connection, not much consideration is being paid particularly, the perception of public universities staff regarding human resource development climate and institutions efficiency. In this regard, the current study was aims to bridge the gaps regarding human resource development practices found in the literature, special reference of Balochistan province, Pakistan.

Study rationale

Empirical research concerning with human resource development climate at public universities level were deficient. In this connection, a lesser amount of attention also been paid to have an examine the public universities status about HRD dimension in Balochistan province. However, particular review of literature exhibits that most of the empirical studies were finished to examine the HRD weather at numerous corporations and no longer lots attention is paid to observe the perception of respondents regarding HRD climate within institutions at Province level.

Objective

- To explore the perception of the respondents about HRD climate at university level.
- To study the perceptions of respondents about capacity building programs as conducted by the universities.
- To identify the foremost complications that hampering the process of achievement in institutions.

Methodology

Descriptive research shows a key starring role in educational circle, descriptive design emphasizes continuing existing condition of phenomena so as to know the behavior of subject (Gall et al., 1996; Knupfer and McLellan, 2001). Present study was conducted in four public universities namely Balochistan University of Engineering and Technology, Khuzdar Balochistan (BUET), Sardar Bahadur Khan Women's University Quetta, Balochistan (SBK), Balochistan University of Information Technology, Engineering and Management Sciences Quetta (BUIITEMS) and University of Balochistan Quetta (UOB). Two hundred (200) respondents as a sample, fifty (50) respondents from each public university were selected by using simple random sampling technique. Sample size for populations was determined by using table given by Fitzgibbon (1987) for “determining the sample size from a given population”. Microsoft Office Excel (2003) and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 used for the data analyses. The data analyzed by calculating frequencies, means, standard deviation, standard error and other rankings assigned by researchers based on mean scores. An analysis of variance analytical technique was applied for the perceptions comparison of the respondents.

Results and discussion

To sum up, this decision unfastened the way for the progress of human resource development dominoes. Table-1: University-wise comparison regarding human resource development climate (N=200).

Categories	Public universities								MS	f-value	Sig*
	BUET		SBK		BUIITEMS		UOB				
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Broad-spectrum HRD climate mechanism	3.26b	1.306	3.46b	.952	3.02b	1.301	2.52a	1.182	1.426	5.763	.001*
Candidness	2.70c	1.074	2.16b	.766	2.00b	.881	1.76a	.555	.706	11.266	.000*
Effective teamwork	2.56a	1.033	2.44a	.993	2.82a	1.190	2.76a	1.205	1.230	1.261	.289 ^{NA}
Expectation	3.18a	1.207	3.32a	.957	3.52a	.995	3.30a	1.055	1.119	.888	.448 ^{NA}
Legitimacy	3.58c	.928	3.72b	.784	3.22c	1.329	2.62a	1.141	1.136	10.605	.000*
Proactivity	3.38b	1.141	3.12b	1.062	3.04b	1.228	2.24a	1.021	1.245	9.714	.000*
Self-sufficiency	2.60a	1.088	2.46a	1.034	2.62a	1.193	2.22a	.910	1.126	1.508	.214 ^{NA}

Scale: 1= Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Undecided, 4= Agree, 5=Strongly agree SD = Standard: MS = Mean square: M = Mean * Significant * alpha level 0.05

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was run to regulate if there was statistically weighty variance among the perceptions of respondents were occurred based on five-point Likert type scale whereas: one (1) stands for “strongly disagree”, two (2) for “disagree”, three (3) stands for “undecided”, four (4) for “agree”, and five (5) stands for “strongly agree” as shown in table-1. Significant variances were observed at 0.05 level. broad-spectrum HRD climate mechanism (F= 5.763; P.05);

candidness (F= 11.266; P.05); legitimacy (F= 10.605; P.05) and proactivity (F= 9.714; P.05). Non-significant variances were perceived about effective teamwork, expectation and self-sufficiency respectively at 0.05 level. Significant discrepancy was observed 4 out of 7 categories

Table-2: University-wise comparison regarding trainings or capacity building programs (N=200).

Categories	Public universities								MS	f-value	Sig*
	BUET		SBK		BUIITEMS		UOB				
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Technology-oriented packages	3.46a	1.110	3.26b	1.157	2.68a	1.285	2.24b	1.061	1.337	11.554	.000*
Employment evaluation process	3.74b	.777	3.76b	.716	3.46b	.930	3.36a	1.005	.748	2.690	.047*
Training and development	2.86b	1.030	2.98b	.958	2.80b	1.309	2.44a	1.128	1.241	2.175	.092 ^{NS}
Presentation review	3.22b	1.282	2.42b	1.052	1.96a	.880	1.90a	.789	1.037	17.909	.000*
Health and safety	3.82b	.691	3.90b	.580	4.02b	.515	3.74a	.751	.411	1.737	.161 ^{NA}
Professional skill	3.88b	.689	3.90b	.505	3.82b	.720	3.54a	.908	.518	2.685	.048*
Research and development aspects	3.76b	.960	3.82b	.661	3.46b	1.073	3.10a	1.074	.915	5.948	.001*

Scale: 1= Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Undecided, 4= Agree, 5=Strongly agree SD = Standard: MS = Mean square: M = Mean
 * Significant * alpha level 0.05

The significant aspect of current research was to determine the capacity building programs and trainings arranged for the respondents. By the way analysis of variance was rummage-sale so as to determine if there was significant variance among the perceptions of the respondents were happened as shown in table-2. The significant variances were detected at 0.05 alpha level. Capacity building programs: **technology-oriented packages** (F= 11.554; P.05); **employment evaluation process** (F= 2.690; P.05); **presentation review** (F= 17.909; P.05) professional skill (F= 2.685; P.05) and **research and development aspects** (F= 5.948; P.05) respectively. On-significant were observed in two categories i.e. **training and development (T&D)** and **health and safety (H&S)**. Significant alterations were detected five out of seven categories.

Table-3: University-wise comparison regarding constraints (N=200).

Categories	Public universities								MS	f-value	Sig*
	BUET		SBK		BUIITEMS		UOB				
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Maintenance the HRD session	2.68a	1.058	2.64a	.964	2.68a	1.269	2.62a	1.227	1.291	.035	.991 ^{NA}
Employment selection process	1.84a	.618	1.92a	.488	1.86a	.756	1.72a	.454	.349	1.006	.391 ^{NA}
Less output process	3.74b	.803	3.86b	.535	3.40a	1.262	3.66b	1.081	.923	2.057	.107 ^{NA}
Ineffective training and compliance	3.68c	1.186	3.20c	1.010	2.66b	1.222	2.24a	.960	1.210	16.298	.000*
Inappropriate health and safety concern	2.20b	.926	2.18b	.629	2.10b	1.074	1.80a	.881	.795	2.154	.095 ^{NA}
Discrimination and diversity	3.88b	.480	3.78b	.679	3.34a	1.255	3.52b	1.111	.875	3.450	.018*
Ineffective accountability about employee queries	2.50b	1.035	2.88c	.961	3.10c	1.093	2.74c	1.084	1.091	2.900	.036*

Scale: 1= Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Undecided, 4= Agree, 5=Strongly agree SD = Standard: MS = Mean square: M = Mean
* Significant * alpha level 0.05

The respondents were asked to delivered their perceptions about constraints faced in the HRD sector. Significant alterations were set up at 0.05 level. Analysis of variance or One Way ANOVA was performed among the largely perceptions of respondents as shown in table-3. Constraints with the term of HRD were: ineffective training and compliance ($F = 16.298, p < 0.05$); discrimination and diversity ($F = 3.450, p < 0.05$); and ineffective accountability about employee queries ($F = 2.900, p < 0.05$). Non- significant variances were found in five categories i.e. maintenance the HRD session, employment selection process, less output process and inappropriate health and safety concern. Significant variances were set up 4 out of 7 about constraints statements.

Conclusions and recommendations

The prime objective of current research was to determine the HRD climate as performed by public universities in Balochistan, province of Pakistan. However, in this connection, based on previous research, resourcing practices, and training and development had been expected to have a positive effect on overall performance, following were the recommendations. Present research study was determining the perceived stimulus of human resource development practices on **climate** of public universities at province level therefore the public universities should have developed to arranged the capacity building programs for employees so as to enhance the staff professional skills, abilities to their work performance. HRD dimension regards as the colossal reassurance tools for enlargement professional capacity, indispensable, part and parcel towards development hierarchy, in this regard HRD practices should be implemented at grass root level so that achieved the desirable output and better conceptual productivity for future development for the employees within work environment.

References:

- i. Dessler, G. 2008. *Human Resource Management (11th edition)*, New Delhi, Prentice Hall, of India private Ltd.
- ii. FINHEEC, (n.d.). *Finnish Higher Education Evaluation Council - Finland*: <http://www.finheec.fi>.
- iii. Fitzgibbon. C. Taylor and L. L. Morris. 1987. *How to Design a Program Evaluation*: Newbury Park, CA: Sage. UK.
- iv. Gall, M. D., Borg, W. R., and Gall, J. P. 1996. *Education research: An introduction (6th ed.)*. White Plains, NY: Longman.
- v. Knoke, D. and Kalleberg, A. L. 1994. *Job Training in U.S. Organizations*, *American Socio-logical Review*, 59: 537-546.
- vi. Knupfer., N. N. and H. McLellan, H. 2001. *An Outline of Chapter 41: "Descriptive Research Methodologies"* Phillip Grace Chapter 41EME 7939.